

CLASSIFICATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE INCREASE OF VALUE ADDED IN FRUIT AND VEGETABLE AGRICULTURAL CLUSTERS

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Abstract. The article highlights the importance of increasing labor productivity in increasing added value and increasing economic efficiency in agricultural enterprises, and that labor productivity in agriculture is the process of reducing labor costs for the production of a unit of output.

Keywords: added value, income and expenditure, innovation, infrastructure, efficiency, economic efficiency, agrocluster, strategy.

Introduction. The importance of high-value-added production in the food supply chain of our country is increasing. As stated in the "Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5853 dated October 23, 2019, "the development of the value-added chain is an important factor in ensuring the competitiveness of agriculture. "The insufficient development of integrated links in the chain of delivery of products from the field to the final consumer, that is, collection, transportation, storage, processing, packaging and certification, limits the possibility of increasing the production of high-value-added products."

In this regard, special attention is being paid to the formation of "agro-industrial clusters" in our republic, aimed at ensuring deep cooperation between farms and processing enterprises. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Clusters and interdependence are the future of Uzbekistan's agriculture. This sector cannot be made competitive without the introduction of science and innovation."

Value added - the value newly created, directly increased, and added to the previous value of the product in a particular firm or enterprise during the production (service) process.

It is determined as the difference between the revenue received from the sale of products, goods, and services produced by a firm and the expenses incurred by the firm to purchase resources (raw materials, semi-finished products) from other firms.

Production efficiency can be determined by how much or little value is added. The higher the amount of value added within an enterprise and sector, the higher the final result.

In Uzbekistan, the concept of Value Added and the practice of calculating it began to be used in the early 1990s.

The fruit and vegetable sector occupies an important place in the republic's agriculture.

It is known that the existing natural and climatic conditions in our country allow for the sustainable development of agricultural products, in particular, fruit and vegetable growing. The high economic and social significance of fruit growing has led to the rapid development of

fruit growing throughout the world. First of all, it is one of the most important sources of this industry, having valuable nutritional and medicinal properties.

When consuming fruits and berries, the population not only receives the necessary vitamins and minerals, but also a complex of important organic acids that ensure the health and longevity of the people. The high economic and social importance of fruit production has led to the rapid development of fruit production throughout the world.

In economic terms, fruit and vegetable growing is one of the main sources of income for the population in rural areas, accounting for 32.2 percent of total agricultural production (8.7 percent of the country's GDP). It has a direct impact on the development of a number of industrial sectors. This sector also occupies a key position in the country's agricultural exports;

In terms of social issues, the effectiveness of sustainable development of fruit and vegetable production has a direct impact not only on the living standards of rural residents, but also on improving the social well-being of all residents of the country.

Increasing value added in agriculture today is proving effective.

1.1.- drawing.

Factors influencing the increase in added value

Increasing labor productivity is essential for increasing added value and increasing economic efficiency in agricultural enterprises.

The economic efficiency of agriculture is largely related to the proper use of land and, on this basis, to increasing productivity. The economic efficiency of the sector is influenced by soil fertility, natural climatic conditions, water supply, the relief of production areas, the proximity of water bodies and many other conditions. These factors have a unique impact on the process of land use in agriculture, and the ability of producers to control them within the limits of their will is limited. In this regard, it is necessary to adapt the production process to the influence of these factors.

Classification of factors affecting product quality

1.1-table

TECHNICAL	ORGANIZATION	ECONOMIC	SOCIAL
-type of manufactured product and its serial production; -condition of technical documentation; -quality of technological devices, equipment and tools; -condition of testing equipment -quality of measuring and control instruments -quality of primary materials, raw materials and components.	-supply of materials, raw materials, etc. -provide technical service of the equipment -planned and consistent work -organize work with suppliers -organize information supply -scientific organization of the workplace, production culture -organize meals and recreation;	form of payment for labor and size of salary -incentive for high-quality products and work -deduction for defects -relationship between product quality, cost and price -economic accounting and organization	-the state of experimental work -selection, placement and replacement of personnel -organization of professional development and training -organization and holding of social competitions -team interaction -transportation and economic conditions -organization of rest during work

Conclusion. The more widely and effectively the achievements of science and technology are used in the agricultural sector, the higher the soil fertility, the lower the contribution of living labor to it, and the greater the contribution of material labor. As a result, the amount of yield per hectare increases, which ultimately becomes the basis for the development of agriculture.

The effective use of the above theoretical foundations in the organization and management of agriculture in farms operating in our country's agricultural sector will provide a solid basis for solving the issues of developing agriculture, creating added value, and increasing economic efficiency in existing farms.

In our opinion, in terms of improving the organization and effective management of fruit and vegetable clusters, it is important to define and fulfill tasks in the following areas:

- development of a program of measures that fully takes into account the interests of the participants of fruit and vegetable clusters, is aimed at ensuring their joint development, and serves to increase added value in the cluster system;
- improvement of organizational and economic mechanisms for managing fruit and vegetable clusters;
- clear definition of the composition of the management company (head enterprise) of fruit and vegetable clusters, its main tasks and functions;
- improvement of contractual relations between participants of fruit and vegetable clusters;
- expanding the economic ties of fruit and vegetable clusters with the state, in particular, through the improvement of tax, credit, customs, and export support mechanisms. One of the main and most important stages of planning, which is one of the important functions in the

management of fruit and vegetable clusters, is the selection of cluster objectives. It should be noted that clusters have broadly expressed goals in multi-level systems.

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